

Simplified two-stage method for the recovery of B-phycoerythrin from *Porphyridium cruentum* and evaluation as a natural food grade colourant

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Abstract

Phycoerythrin (B-PE) is one of the most characteristic phycobiliproteins; its commercial use depends on its degree of purity. In this work, a simple methodology based on tangential flow ultrafiltration has been developed for the extraction, concentration, and partial purification of B-PE from *Porphyridium cruentum*. It was possible to extract up to 84% of the B-PE contained in the biomass using buffer phosphate (0.1 M pH 5.5) as a solvent. However, the purity ratio remained lower than 0.29. Ultrafiltration membranes of molecular weights of 10, 50, and 100 KDa (MWCO) were tested for concentration and purification purposes. The best results were obtained with the smallest pore size (10 KDa), achieving a purity ratio of 0.70, 84% recovery, a global yield of 71% and a final concentration of 0.21 mg·mL⁻¹ (14-fold concentration). The specific permeate rate and resistance to filtration under these conditions were also analysed. The overall process resulted in a B-PE recovery yield of 71%. Two preservatives were evaluated to improve the stability of the obtained aqueous solution. Their performance was evaluated at different temperatures and radiation exposure conditions. The stability of the B-PE solution determined as the lifespan at 25 °C was increased from the initial value of 40 days to 75 and 133 days by the addition of glucose and carrageenan, respectively. In the same way, the stability of the protein increased with the use of these two additives in additional experiments at 4 and 42 °C. Overall, these results demonstrate that the use of a two-step system consisting of initial clarification followed by ultrafiltration constitutes a simple and scalable method to obtain BPE colouring extracts with food-grade purity.

Keywords: Phycobiliproteins, food colourants, filtration, membranes, microalgae, biorefinery.

1. Introduction

The term microalgae is generally used to refer to unicellular eukaryotic photosynthetic organisms and prokaryotic cyanobacteria. These microorganisms have many very attractive features for large-scale sustainable production. These include their capacity to transform carbon dioxide into valuable products (biomass), the potential of growing or producing them on non-arable land and using non-drinkable water (seawater or wastewater), and their fast growth capacity, which exceeds that of terrestrial plants. Microalgae can be used as feedstock for many valuable commercial products, including proteins, lipids, and pigments. The latter is especially attractive because of the increasing consumer demand for natural colours in foods and their dual role: together with colour, they can provide bioactive properties such as antioxidant or antimicrobial activities, among others (Singh et al. 2005). This consideration has become a relevant issue as most consumers suffer from chemophobia, rejecting current chemically made chemicals and additives, encouraging industries to seek natural compounds for application in the food and pharmaceutical sectors (Castro-Muñoz et al. 2024; Garza-Cadena et al. 2023; Hernández-Pinto et al. 2024). In this sense, the most important pigments produced by microalgae are chlorophylls, carotenoids, and phycobiliproteins (Begum et al. 2016).

Phycoerythrin is a water-soluble accessory photosynthetic pigment that is part of the phycobiliprotein family and is predominant in some rhodophytes, cryptophytes, and cyanobacteria (Tan et al. 2023). Phycoerythrins are classified into three main types based on their different spectral properties and the organisms that produce them: B-phycoerythrin (B-PE), C-phycoerythrin (C-PE), and R-phycoerythrin (R-PE). From a commercial perspective, B-PE is one of the few existing natural pink pigments and shows potential for use as an edible food colourant (Carmona et al. 2022). B-PE has also been suggested as a health-promoting compound antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticarcinogenic properties *in vitro*, among others (Sudhakar et al. 2023).

The phycoerythrin market is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.2% until 2032 and increase from US\$ 4.2 million in 2022 to US\$ 7.6 million in 2032.

The market value and potential applications of B-PE extracts are largely dependent on their purity, typically measured as the ratio between the absorbance of the extracts at 545 nm (the B-PE visible absorption peak of B-PE) and 280 nm (the uv absorption peak related to the total protein content) (Ji et al. 2022). Phycobiliproteins with purity >0.7 are considered food grade, > 1.5 cosmetic grade, >3.0 reagent grade and >4.0 analytical grade (Lauceri et al. 2023). The market price of purified B-PE today varies from 30 to 150 US\$.mg⁻¹ (Ruiz-Ruiz et al. 2013), although there are lower purity phycoerythrin-rich powders in the range of 120-130 US\$.kg⁻¹ (Shaanxi Natural Healthcare Group Co., China). Despite growing market interest and demand, industrial production of phycobiliproteins, in general, is still limited by production costs and the lack of purification and stabilisation processes (Lauceri et al. 2023).

To recover B-PE, methodologies such as precipitation using ammonium sulphate, filtration, aqueous two-phase extraction, chromatography, or combinations of these techniques with pulsed electric fields or ultrasounds are often employed (George and John 2023). There is still significant controversy about the best approach for obtaining B-PE, and it is not yet clear which methods and/or combinations of methods are most suitable for the purification of this valuable pigment at medium and large scales. It is important to note that many of the techniques used so far are hardly scalable, and only those based on scalable systems are of real interest from an industrial perspective. Extraction and purification processes based on membrane technologies are among the most promising methodologies, due to the sustainability of this type of extraction and purification techniques. Although these processes do not have high selectivity with respect to the compound to be obtained, are associated with simple equipment and conveniently compact structures, are highly adaptable, require low energy input, and have a lower environmental impact compared to traditional technologies (Xie et al. 2021). In addition, the use of integrated membranes systems offer advantages over the conventional methodologies: they do not involve phase changes, chemical additives and heat treatment, they are modular and easy to scale up, and are characterised by a separation selectivity suitable for certain applications, thus

enabling a more rational utilisation of raw materials and recovery and reuse of byproducts (Cassano et al. 2015; Díaz-Montes et al. 2020).

One of the major challenges of natural pigments such as B-PE is their stability, which is lower than that of their synthetic counterparts. Several additives demonstrated the capacity to increase the stability of natural pigments including phycobiliproteins, especially phycocyanin. Compounds such as sugars, acids, salts, protein cross-linkers, and biocides have been reported as potential stabilisers. For example, citric acid increased the stability of phycocyanin extracted from *Arthrospira platensis* at different temperatures for more than a month (Mishra et al. 2008) and glucose and sucrose increased the half-life of phycocyanin from 19 to 33-44 min after heating at 60 °C for 15 min (Chaiklahan et al. 2012). The best stabilisation process for commercial-scale production depends on its intended application (e.g., pH and temperature variations, shelf-life length).

To address some of the main obstacles that limit the commercial exploitation of B-PE, this work developed a simple and scalable two-stage process for extracting B-PE for use in food applications. The first stage involved an osmotic shock clarification process and the second stage consisted of the fractionation of the extract using membrane technologies. This work also evaluated the stability of the extract and how it was affected after the incorporation of different additives, such as glucose and carrageenan.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and reagents used

The microalga used as the source of B-PE was *Porphyridium cruentum* UTEX 161 from the UTEX Culture Collection of Algae (The University of Texas at Austin, USA). The microalga was produced in winter at the University of Almeria (Almeria, Spain) using 3.6 m³ tubular photobioreactors located within a greenhouse. The nutrients used for the biomass production were commercial fertilisers purchased from a local retailer. The composition of the culture medium consisted of 0.9 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄, and 20 mg·L⁻¹ of Karentol[®] (Konegard, Barcelona, Spain) which is a commercial mixture of

micronutrients. The pH during the biomass production was set at 8.0 and controlled by on-demand injection of carbon dioxide. Three independent photobioreactors located inside the same greenhouse were used, being each photobioreactor the experimental unit. Extracts fractionation was done using 10, 50, and 100 kDa molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) Vivaflow® tangential flow filtration cassettes (Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany), consisting of polyethersulfone membranes (PES).

2.2. B-PE extraction and concentration

A phycobiliprotein-rich extract was recovered following a previously described methodology (Carmona et al. 2022) with minor modifications. Briefly, 2.0 ± 0.0 g of freeze-dried biomass of *P. cruentum* were suspended in 100 mL of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 5.5) and stirred at 350 rpm for 15 min using a RZR1 stirrer (Heidolph, Schwabach, Germany). The suspension was centrifuged using a Medtronic BL-S centrifuge (JP Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) operating at 12,000 rpm and 4 °C for 15 min.

The crude phycoerythrin extract obtained as described above was used as a sample to feed the tangential ultrafiltration membrane system (UF), membranes with different pore sizes of 10, 50 and 100 kDa being tested. The system consisted of a reservoir for the sample to be filtered, a peristaltic pump and the UF membranes (Sartorius Vivaflow 200). The main objective was to obtain a retentate (food grade extract of phycoerythrin) and a filtrate (waste) containing the smaller molecules that are not of interest and have passed through the pores of the membranes. Ultrafiltration was carried out through polyethersulfone membranes (PES, fibre length 30 cm, fibre diameter lumen 1 mm; membrane surface 0.02 m²), at a constant pressure of 1.0 bar. During the development of the UF process, samples of the concentrate were taken at regular intervals to analyse their concentration and purity, in addition to measuring the flow rate as the experiment progressed. Once the initial feed volume (500 mL) reached its minimum (6 mL), the contents of the pipes and membranes were flushed with phosphate buffer to achieve maximum reuse of the purified B-PE extract (with a final volume of approximately 50 mL). The entire process was carried out at room temperature.

The same biomass was subjected to quantitative extraction to determine the total phycoerythrin content of the biomass. The process consisted of a repetitive extraction using osmotic shock with buffer until no biliproteins were detected in the supernatant after centrifugation. Phycobiliproteins were detected by performing the corresponding UV-visible absorption spectrum in the 250-700 nm range. When no or negligible signal was obtained when recording the spectrum, it was concluded that the protein was no longer present in the medium. The procedure was carried out using the previously published methodology until total depletion of the biomass in phycoerythrin (Carmona et al. 2022).

2.3. Characterisation of the B-PE extract

The concentrations of phycobiliproteins, namely phycocyanin [$R - PC$], allophycocyanin [APC], and phycoerythrin [$B - PE$] were estimated using the following equations (Román et al. 2002):

$$[R - PC](mg/mL) = \frac{A_{620} - 0.7 \cdot A_{650}}{7.38} \quad (1)$$

$$[APC](mg/mL) = \frac{A_{650} - 0.19 \cdot A_{620}}{5.65} \quad (2)$$

$$[B - PE](mg/mL) = \frac{A_{565} - 2.8 \cdot [R - PC] - 1.34 \cdot [APC]}{12.7} \quad (3)$$

where A_{620} , A_{650} , and A_{565} were the absorbance measured at 620, 650, and 565 nm, respectively using a Lambda 20 spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer, MA, USA). Three technical determinations were taken per natural replicate. The B-PE purity was determined using the next equation where the absorbances were measured at 545 and 280 nm:

$$B - PE \text{ purity} = \frac{A_{545}}{A_{280}} \quad (4)$$

In addition, the concentration factor was calculated as the ratio between the final concentration in the membranes' outlet and the initial concentration of the extract in the membranes' inlet.

2.4. Characterisation of the performance of the membrane

To characterise the performance of the membrane, two main parameters were calculated. The first was the specific flow rate (J) (permeate flux) or the volume of suspension that

passes through the membrane per unit surface and time (J , $L \cdot m^{-2} \cdot h^{-1}$). The second was the resistance of the filtration (R) calculated as the ratio between the pressure of filtration (1 bar was chosen as the transmembrane pressure in all the experiments) and the specific flow rate (R , $bar \cdot h \cdot m^{-1}$). Both parameters were calculated using the following equations:

$$J \left(\frac{L}{m^2 \cdot h} \right) = \frac{\text{Flow rate (L/h)}}{\text{Membrane surface (m}^2\text{)}} \quad (5)$$

$$R \left(\frac{bar \cdot h}{m} \right) = \frac{\text{Transmembrane pressure (bar)}}{\text{Specific flow rate} \left(\frac{L}{m^2 \cdot h} \right)} \quad (6)$$

2.5. Stability of the B-PE extract

The effect of different additives (glucose and carrageenan) on the stability of B-PE was determined by kinetic tests. The tests lasted 40 days and were carried out at different temperatures (4, 25, and 42 °C) and in the dark. The data were fitted to the first-order kinetic equation. The degradation rate constant (k) was determined using the following equation:

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} \right) = -kt \quad (7)$$

where C_t was the concentration of B-PE at time t , and C_0 was the initial concentration. Once k was determined, the predicted time necessary to reduce the concentration of B-PE by 50% ($t_{1/2}$) was calculated using the equation:

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k} \quad (8)$$

where k was the degradation rate constant.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The data were analysed using analysis of variance using SPSS Statistics 22 (IBM, USA). A Tukey HSD test was carried out to identify where the sample differences occurred. The criterion for statistical significance was $p < 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Extraction and purification of B-PE

The biomass of *Porphyridium cruentum* was analysed to determine the total content of phycobiliproteins (B-PE and R-PC), with the results showing that the biomass contained up to 1% by weight of these compounds. Among the different methods proposed for the extraction of B-PE, solubilisation in buffer phosphate has been shown to be highly efficient and contributed to the stabilisation of B-PE. The proposed extraction method consisted of mixing the biomass with the buffer and stirring the mixture so that cell rupture occurred through an osmotic shock. After centrifugation, a supernatant containing up to 84% of the B-PE contained in the biomass was obtained. This extract also contained up to 18.8% of the R-PC present in the biomass, among other soluble compounds mainly proteins. R-PC is a common phycobiliprotein present in some microalgae, especially in cyanobacteria, and is currently being used as a food colourant and has shown health-promoting effects (Villaró-Cos, Guzmán Sánchez, et al. 2024). It is important to note that the third phycobiliprotein that usually accompanies B-PE and R-PC is APC. In this case, it was not detected because of its low intracellular concentration and its strong union with photosystem II through the core-membrane complex (Peña-Medina et al. 2023). The concentration of this B-PE extract was $0.015 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and its degree of purity was 0.29, defined as the absorbance ratio at 545 and 280 nm, respectively. The obtained B-PE concentration was lower than in previous work using *Gracilaria corticata* ($0.15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) where the extract was tested for biomedical applications and showed potential for further study as an anticarcinogenic agent (Sudhakar et al. 2023). The content of bioactive molecules depends on the strain used and also on operational and environmental conditions during biomass production (Villaró-Cos, Cuaresma Franco, et al. 2024).

The obtained B-PE extract did not meet the purity and concentration requirements to be used for commercial purposes. To solve this problem, the use of ultrafiltration was proposed. The suspension was then passed through membranes with different pore sizes (10, 50 or 100 kDa MWCO) to concentrate the target compound (B-PE, molecular weight 240 kDa) in the retentate allowing the impurities to pass through the membrane, promoting the corresponding purification (Figure 1). To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the

first time that the purification of B-PE by tangential filtration has been reported using such a simple and easy to scale methodology. The process developed in this work is simpler than previous processes described in the literature. For example, a previous study evaluated the use of membranes to recover B-PE and polysaccharides from *P. cruentum* achieving a recovery of 48% (and a purity index of 2.3) using two filtration steps (Marcati et al. 2014). Purification of other phycobiliproteins, such as phycocyanin, has been widely investigated. For example, a previous study developed a 3-step filtration process (5 μm , 0.8/0.2 μm , and 50 kDa) that allowed recovering 73% of the phycocyanin present in *Arthrospira platensis* (Spirulina) with a purity ratio of 1.0 (Chaiklahan et al. 2011). Similarly, a recovery of 23% and a purity ratio of 0.76 were achieved in a different study using 0.4 μm and 60 kDa membranes (Brião et al. 2020).

The experiments performed demonstrated that the proposed technology is suitable, allowing the concentration of the initial suspension to be increased from 500 mL to 6 mL. Depending on the membrane pore size (10, 50 or 100 kDa), the final concentration of B-PE ranged from 0.19 to 0.21 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ (concentration factor from 12 to 14) and purity from 0.64 to 0.70 (Table 1). The recovery of B-PE was reduced when the membrane pore size increased, although it was greater than 80% for of 10 and 50 kDa pore sizes. Overall, the purification process using 10 kDa MWCO membranes led to a maximum global recovery of 71% of the B-PE present in the biomass of *P. cruentum*. The global yield of the B-PE purification process consisting of two stages (clarification and UF) is the result of multiplying the recovery values of both stages, with the recovery defined as the amount of protein of interest obtained after a step compared to the amount in the sample before treatment at that step.

The time necessary to achieve this purification was longer when the smaller pore-size membrane was used. The purity ratio achieved was comparable when using 10 and 50 kDa. However, the purity of the extract was lower when 100 kDa membranes were used. This can be attributed to a lower retention of B-PE, whose native hexameric form has an average

molecular weight of 240 kDa (Nguyen et al. 2020), but monomeric and dimeric forms of the protein can have a molecular weight below 100 kDa. For example, the molecular masses of the α and β subunits are 21 kDa and the molecular mass of the γ subunit is 38 kDa (Orta-Ramirez et al. 2000). In addition, the retention of the membranes is not 100%, and this loss of protein through the filtrate, which generates a certain pink colour in the filtrate line, may be due to an equilibrium of protein in which, in addition to the protein in the hexameric state (240 Kda), molecules in the dimeric state (80 Kda) that could pass through the pore size (100 Kda) were also present.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the concentration of B-PE, the concentration factor, and the purity ratio of the extracts during the purification process (volume of suspension variation from 500 ml to 6 ml). As expected, the concentration of B-PE and the concentration factors increased exponentially when the volume of suspension was reduced during the filtration process. A similar trend was observed when 10 and 50 kDa membranes were used, indicating that both pore sizes are adequate for this application. In terms of purity, both pore sizes produce 0.71 and 0.73 purity ratios values, which are accepted as suitable for food applications. However, the greatest difference was observed in terms of global yield, obtaining the best value using the 10 kDa membrane with a value achieved of 71 %.

3.2. Analysis of membrane filtration step

To better understand the ultrafiltration process, the variation of the specific flow rate and resistance to filtration were analysed during the experiments (Figure 3). As expected, results showed that the specific permeate rate was higher with the larger the pore size of the membrane utilised. Referring to the flow resistance, it could be seen that the highest resistance occurred in the membrane with the smallest pore size (10 Kda) and the lowest in the membrane with the largest pore size (100 Kda). Furthermore, the flux resistance values remained more or less constant after the first minutes of operation for the 10 and 50 KDa membranes, respectively, while they increase progressively when using the 100 KDa membrane. This suggests that the membrane collapsed during the operation due to the penetration of materials in the pores of the membranes, indicating that these materials are

in the range of 100 kDa (Zin et al. 2016). Avoiding fouling is one of the major challenges of membrane bioreactors and processes (Du et al. 2020). The results related to the resistance to the filtration confirm this behaviour. The highest resistance of $43 \text{ bar}\cdot\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ was measured when using the membrane with the smaller pore size, while this value was reduced to 23 and $16 \text{ bar}\cdot\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ when using 50 and 100 kDa membranes, respectively. The resistance to filtration includes both the specific resistance of the membrane and the one corresponding to the solution, which normally is a function of the concentration of compounds and the rheological properties of the solution. To elucidate the relationship between these variables will require a special work plan, but it must be performed once the industrial setup is defined, which is outside the scope of this study. It is important to mention that the optimisation of the process at a larger scale will require optimising the pore size and properties of the membrane (mechanical construction, operation mode/conditions, etc.), especially to maximise the specific permeate rate to minimise the time of the operation while reducing the resistance of the filtration to reduce the energy consumption of the overall process. That optimisation process must be performed once the final membranes and their configuration are selected, because these results are largely dependent on the type and technology of the membrane selected.

3.3. Stability of the B-PE extracts

The stability of natural pigments, such as those obtained from microalgae, is lower compared to that of their synthetic counterparts. This represents a challenge for their commercial implementation. For this reason, several studies have attempted to increase the stability of natural pigments using additives that increase their shelf life or by applying milder processing techniques during food manufacture that avoid or minimise colour degradation (Pez Jaeschke et al. 2021). Furthermore, the extraction, purification, and storage of extracts can also affect their bioactive properties. For example, recent work revealed that ultrafiltration of phycocyanin increased the purity ratio of phycocyanin from 0.53 to 0.76, but led to a 30% decrease in its antioxidant activity (Brião et al. 2020). Similarly, ultrasounds can also negatively affect the quality of extracts (Fratelli et al. 2021).

In this work, different additives that showed potential for increasing the stability of other phycobiliproteins were investigated at different storage temperatures. Table 2 summarises the kinetic parameters related to the stability of the B-PE solutions obtained as a function of the different temperatures and additives evaluated. A B-PE solution in buffer phosphate (pH 7.0 and 50 mM) was compared with B-PE solutions with additives. The additives used (glucose and carrageenan) were food grade materials and the temperatures evaluated were 4 °C, 25 °C and 42 °C. Carrageenan and glucose are polysaccharides used in foods because their interaction with proteins has been widely used as a useful tool to stabilise these matrices. Thus, the protein-polysaccharide interaction leads to a mechanism of complex formation that increases the stability of proteins against heating or acid degradation. This complexation mechanism is attributed to the electrostatic interactions generated in the medium, which are dependent on the isoelectric points of the proteins and the pH of the médium (Buecker et al. 2022). Overall, the use of additives had a significant effect on the stability of B-PE ($p < 0.05$). The value of $t_{1/2}$ in the absence of additives was 40 days at 25 °C. The addition of 2.5 mM carrageenan to the solution led to an increase in $t_{1/2}$ to 133 days, representing a 343.3% increase. Glucose also improved stability, with an increase in $t_{1/2}$ of 58.7, 87.5 and 200.0 % at 4, 25, and 42 °C, respectively. Storage temperature also had a significant effect on the stability of B-PE. As expected, the higher the temperature, the lower the stability. In the absence of additives, $t_{1/2}$ decreased from 63 days when stored at 4 °C to 9 days when stored at 42 °C, which is consistent with previous studies that demonstrated the striking effect of temperature on the stability of natural colourants (Ghidouche et al. 2013). Similar results were obtained in previous studies using phycobiliproteins. For example, a previous study evaluated different additives including benzoic acid, citric acid, sucrose, calcium chloride, and ascorbic acid and observed that benzoic acid showed the best preservative effect of both phycocyanin and phycoerythrin at 4 °C, achieving $t_{1/2}$ values of up to 630 days (Kannaujiya and Sinha 2016). Similarly, in a previous work, the stability of phycocyanin increased 10 times at room temperature and 3

times after thermal treatment when sodium chloride was added at a concentration of 2.5% (Chaiklahan et al. 2012).

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated the extraction and purification of food-grade B-PE from the microalga *P. cruentum* following a process based on an initial clarification step followed by membrane ultrafiltration. The process developed was able to achieve a high concentration of B-PE with a global recovery of 71% and a purity ratio of 0.7, which is high enough for use in food applications. The results obtained showed that the three types of membranes used were capable of obtaining a protein extract with a food grade purity ratio, with the 10 Kda membrane offering the best overall yield and concentration factor values. The stability of the extract was also studied with the aim of increasing its shelf life. In this sense, the stability of B-PE was significantly improved by using food-grade additives such as carrageenan, which allowed increasing the $t_{1/2}$ to 144 days, although stability was found to be temperature dependent. Lower storage temperatures led to higher stability of B-PE, this effect being due to the fact that higher temperatures promote faster protein denaturation. The results indicated that this approach can represent a useful method for B-PE purification, facilitating its scaling up because of to the simplicity of the procedure. Future studies will evaluate the colouring potential of the purified extract in real food matrices as well as the colour stability during storage.

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Declaration of competing interest

Authors declare no conflict of interests

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on reasonable request from the corresponding author.

Table 1. B-PE purification process performance using different MWCO membranes. The process finished when the volume was 10% of its initial value. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD.

Step	Recovery (%)	Concentration Factor	[B-PE] (mg·mL⁻¹)	Purity Ratio	Global Yield (%)	Time (min)
Clarification	84 \pm 2		0.015 \pm 0.001	0.29 \pm 0.01		
10 KDa	84 \pm 2	14 \pm 1	0.210 \pm 0.020	0.70 \pm 0.01	71 \pm 2	76
50 KDa	80 \pm 2	13 \pm 1	0.200 \pm 0.020	0.73 \pm 0.01	67 \pm 2	37
100 KDa	76 \pm 2	12 \pm 1	0.190 \pm 0.020	0.64 \pm 0.01	64 \pm 2	25

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of B-PE stability as a function of temperature and additives. B-PE buffer solution was compared with B-PE buffers solutions added with glucose and carrageenan.

Temperature		B-PE	B-PE + Glucose	B-PE + Carrageenan
4 °C	k (days ⁻¹)	0.011	0.0069	0.0048
	t _{1/2} (days)	63	100	144
25 °C	k (days ⁻¹)	0.017	0.0092	0.0052
	t _{1/2} (days)	40	75	133
42 °C	k (days ⁻¹)	0.073	0.0255	0.019
	t _{1/2} (days)	9	27	36

Figure legends

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the B-PE purification methodology.

Figure 2. Evolution of the (A) B-PE concentration, (B) concentration factor, and (C) purity ratio during filtration as a function of the pore size of the membrane utilized. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 3. Variation of (A) the specific permeate rate and (B) resistance of filtration during filtration as a function of the pore size of the membrane utilized. Transmembrane pressure = 1 bar. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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